

Confirmatory analyses

Synthetic cannabinoid
infused onto seized paper

GC-MS
ESI-MS
¹H NMR

ADB-5'Br-Butinaca

Raman Confocal Direct Analyses

Synthetic cannabinoid
infused onto seized paper

**Dispersive
Raman Microscope**

Raw spectrum

Material storage
for counterevidence

Raman Difference Spectroscopy (RDS)

Synthetic cannabinoid
infused onto seized paper

Methanol-solubilized
compound and filtration

Washed
paper

FT-Raman

RDS

Residual spectrum

Recrystallized
compound on paper

Complementary Analyses

FT-IR ATR and UV-Vis
via difference

Theoretical Calculation

Raman
FT-IR
UV-Vis
Structural

Vibrational Assignment

Raman Analytical Detection:
1H-indazole-3-carboxamide

Inter-instrument agreement

Raw spectrum **Residual spectrum**